

Supplementary Figure 1. Membrane topology of MtLysX and SaMprF. A) Schematic representation of MtLysX (Rv1640c) membrane topology as predicted by HMMTOP and relative activities of the four different fusions of MtLysX (light gray bars) to either *phoA* or *lacZ* (white). β -galactosidase activities (β -gal) were normalized relative to that of fusion E whereas alkaline phosphatase activities (AP) were normalized relative to that of fusion D. The LysU domain of MtLysX [10] is highlighted in black and pointed by a thick black arrow. B) Schematic representation of SaMprF membrane topology as predicted by TMHMM and relative activities of the two different fusions of SaMprF (gray bars) to either *phoA* or *lacZ* (white). β -galactosidase activities (β -gal) were normalized relative to that of fusion H whereas alkaline phosphatase activities (AP) were normalized relative to that of MtLysX fusion D. Relative activities are representative of two independent experiments. The Lys-PG synthase domain of MtLysX and SaMprF is highlighted in dark grey and pointed by a thick gray arrow. IN: inside the cytoplasm. OUT: outside the cytoplasm. The *phoA/lacZ* moiety is not drawn on scale as the two genes have a different length. Numbers indicate amino acid positions.

Supplementary Figure 2. Minimum inhibitory concentration of HNP-1 in *M. smegmatis* expressing MtLysX2 (MS322, dotted line) compared to the parental strain (MS321, squared line). Error bars derive from two independent experiments.

Supplementary Figure 3. Killing assay with hydrogen peroxide. Killing assay of *M. smegmatis* mc²155::Mt_lysX2 (MS322, dark gray) and mc²155::pROL_Hyg (MS321 light gray) with 5mM H₂O₂.

Supplementary Figure 4. Killing assay of *M. smegmatis* mc²155::Mt_lysX2 (MS322, dark gray) and mc²155::pROL_Hyg (light gray) at pH 4.5. Strains were grown for 24 h in Sauton medium at pH 6.8 (A), and 7H9 at pH 5.5 (B) before being transferred into the same medium at pH 4.5.

Supplementary Figure 5. Growth curve of MS321 and MS322 in Sauton medium pH 5.5. The growth curve is representative of two independent experiments.

Supplementary Figure 6. Biofilm formation in Sauton medium pH 6.8. Bacteria, grown to stationary phase were diluted 1:100 in Sauton pH 6.8. 4 ml of the suspension were then inoculated in a 24-well plate and

incubated at 37°C. Pictures were taken after 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 days (D). The experiment was repeated twice in triplicate and comparable results were obtained.

Supplementary Figure 7. Expression of *MtlsX2* in *M. smegmatis*. The image shows an ethidium-bromide-stained gel of the RT-PCR products, separated by 2% agarose gel electrophoresis. M, molecular mass marker; 1, H₂O; 2, RNA from MS322; 3, cDNA from MS322; 4, cDNA from MS321; 5, DNA from *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv.

Supplementary Table S1. List of primers. Sequences recognized by the restriction enzymes used in this work are underlined. RBS is highlighted in italics. Sequences annealing to *M. tuberculosis* are highlighted in bold.

Mt_lysX2::phoA

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
RP578	<u>GAGCTC</u> <i>T</i> TAAAGAAGGAGATATACATAT GGTGGC AGCGGCCGGCGAGC	forward	SacI, NdeI	fusion A
RP582	CATATGGTGGCAGCGGCCGGCGAGC	forward	NdeI	fusion B and C
RP583	<u>GTCGAC</u> AGGCCGCGGT <i>CGCATGCATGGC</i>	reverse	Sall	fusion A
RP585	<u>GTCGAC</u> AGTGACACATGGCCGCGAAGT <i>CG</i>	reverse	Sall	fusion B
RP587	<u>GTCGAC</u> AGATCAACGCACGGCAGACACGCT	reverse	Sall	fusion C

Mt_lysX2::lacZ

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
RP580	<u>GAATTC</u> <i>T</i> TAAAGAAGGAGATATACATAT GGTGGC AGCGGCCGGCGAGC	forward	EcoRI, NdeI	fusion A
RP1454	TATACATAT GGTGGCAGCGGCCGGCGAGC	forward	NdeI	fusion B and C
RP584	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>TTGGCCGCGGT</i> <i>CGCATGCATGGC</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion A
RP586	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>ACGTGACACATGGCCGCGAAGT</i> <i>CG</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion B
RP588	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>AAGATCAACGCACGGCAGACACGCT</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion C

Mt_lysX::phoA

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
RP1508	<u>GAGCTC</u> <i>T</i> TAAAGAAGGAGATATACATAT GGGACT CCACTTAACTGTCCCTGGCCTTC	forward	SacI, NdeI	fusion D
RP1510	CATATGGGACTCCACTTAACTGTCCCTGGCCTT	forward	NdeI	fusion E, F, and G
RP1509	<u>TCTAGAT</u> GGGATCGGCGAGGGCGAATC	reverse	XbaI	fusion D
RP1511	<u>TCTAGAC</u> CCACCAGCAGGCAGTCGGAGTC	reverse	XbaI	fusion E
RP1512	<u>TCTAGAT</u> GTTGGAGCGGTAGAGCGTCTCGA	reverse	XbaI	fusion F
RP1513	<u>TCTAGAT</u> TACTTGCCGCAGCCCGCTCACGTC	reverse	XbaI	fusion G

Mt_lysX::lacZ

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
RP1514	<u>GATATC</u> <i>T</i> TAAAGAAGGAGATATACATAT GGGACTC CACTTAACTGTCCCTGGCCTTC	forward	EcoRV, NdeI	fusion D
RP1510	CATATGGGACTCCACTTAACTGTCCCTGGCCTT	forward	NdeI	fusion E, F, and G
RP1515	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>TTGGGATCGGCGAGGGCGAATC</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion D
RP1516	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>TCCACCAGCAGGCAGTCGGAGTC</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion E
RP1517	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>TGTTGGAGAGGTAGAGCGTCTCGA</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion F
RP1518	<u>GGATCC</u> <i>TTTACTTGCCGCAGCCCGCTCACGTC</i>	reverse	BamHI	fusion G

Sa mprF::phoA

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
RP1581	AACATATGAATCAGGAAGTTAAAAACAAA	forward	SacI	fusion H and I
RP1582	AAGGATCCTAGAAAGAAATACGTACTTTGCTAA	reverse	BamHI	fusion H
RP1583	AAGGATCCCGAAATTATGATATAAAGGCATGT	reverse	BamHI	fusion I

Sa mprF::lacZ

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
RP1578	AACATATGAATCAGGAAGTTAAAAACAAA	forward	EcoRI	fusion H and I
RP1579	AAGGATCCTTAGAAGAAATACGTACTTTGCTAA	reverse	BamHI	fusion H
RP1580	AAGGATCCCGAAATTATGATATAAAGGCAT	reverse	BamHI	fusion I

M. smegmatis::Mt_lysX2

Primer name	Sequence	Primer orientation	Restriction enzymes	PCR fragment
Rv1619up	GTTGGGATCCGGGCACTTT	forward	BamHI	lysX2+172 bp upstream
Rv1619low	TGCGCCAAGCTTTCATAG	reverse	HindIII	lysX2+172 bp upstream
Rv1619a	GTGACTGTGAAGCTGC	forward		lysX2 355bp fragment
Rv1619b	CGGCTATCAGAATCTCACC	reverse		lysX2 355bp fragment